

Popular Article

An overview of Brucella vaccines

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Abstract

Brucellosis is a worldwide zoonosis affecting both animal and human health. Till now, there is no effective vaccine licensed for brucellosis in humans. The current animal vaccines are S19, Rev.1, S2, RB51, and SR82, besides M5, H38, and 45/20 were once used to prevent animal brucellosis. These vaccines still have a number of shortcomings, though, including residual pathogenicity and interference with common serological testing. With the development of DNA recombination technologies and the completion of the sequence of Brucella genome, much effort has been undertaken for the development of new vaccines, safer and more effective, that could also be used in other susceptible species of animals.

Introduction

Brucellosis is one of the most important zoonotic diseases affecting several host species and is caused by multiple Brucella spp making the disease more complicated. The disease is caused by facultative intracellular Gram-negative bacteria of different Brucella species. In human disease is mainly characterized by undulating fever which may progress to arthritis, endocarditic, osteomyelitis, in some cases. Bovine brucellosis is mainly characterized by abortion and infertility. Therefore, bovine brucellosis results in very significant economic losses. Animal brucellosis control and prevention is largely based on vaccination. Therefore, over the past decades there has been an intensive research effort for developing safer and more efficacious vaccines against brucellosis.

Live attenuated vaccines

Animal vaccination against brucellosis is mostly on live attenuated vaccine including *Brucella abortus* S19, *Brucella abortus* RB51, and *Brucella melitensis* Rev.1.

***Brucella abortus* strain 19 vaccine:** A widely used vaccine for the prevention of brucellosis in cattle is *B. abortus* S19, which remains the reference vaccine with which any other vaccines must be compared. *Brucella abortus* S19 was isolated in 1923 from milk of a Jersey cow by Dr John Buck, experimentally evaluated in 1930s, is one of the most successful vaccines extensively used throughout the world for control of bovine brucellosis. It is used as a live vaccine and is normally given to female calves aged between 3 and 6 months as a single subcutaneous dose of $5-8 \times 10^{10}$ viable organisms. Though the vaccination for adult is not followed in many countries due to persistent antibody titer, but a reduced dose of from 3×10^8 to 5×10^9 organisms may be administered subcutaneously to adult cattle. The vaccine is made from smooth strain of *Brucella abortus* strain 19. But due to strong reactivity towards the O-side chain, vaccinated animals cannot be differentiated from infected animals by commonly used test. The lower rate of abortion due to vaccination is also possible.

***Brucella abortus* strain RB51 vaccine:** RB51 is a spontaneous rough mutant obtained by subculturing the virulent strain *B. abortus* 2308 on rifampicin and penicillin containing media. The mutant strain has an *IS711* element disrupting the *wboA* gene encoding a glycosyl transferase responsible for O-side chain synthesis making it a rough phenotype. Since 1996, *B. abortus* strain RB51 is routinely used for prevention of brucellosis in cattle in many countries. However, there is a disagreement over the protective performance of strain RB51 compared with strain S19 in cattle. Each country uses slightly different methods to apply this vaccine. In the USA (a country that was almost free of bovine brucellosis before RB51 was introduced), calves are vaccinated subcutaneously between the ages of 4 and 12 months with $1-3.4 \times 10^{10}$ viable organisms. Vaccination of cattle over 12 months of age is carried out only under authorization from the State or Federal Animal Health Officials, and the recommended dose is $1-3 \times 10^9$ viable organisms. In other countries, it is used for calfhod vaccination to vaccinate female calves (4-12 months of age) with a $1-3.4 \times 10^{10}$ dose, with revaccination from 12 months of age onwards with a similar dose. Field experience also indicates that it can induce abortion and increased perinatal mortality if applied to pregnant cattle. Rough strain RB51 is less virulent and it does not induce a positive response in typical serological diagnostic test thus can be used as DIVA vaccine for eradication of disease.

***Brucella melitensis* strain Rev.1:** Rev.1 strain is a vaccine strain used for vaccination of ruminants. Subcutaneous or conjunctival immunization with *B. melitensis* Rev. 1 confers adequate immunity in small ruminants. *B. melitensis* Rev. 1 induces a positive antibody response in serological tests in vaccinated animals. By contrast, the rough *B. abortus* RB51 vaccine is not effective against *B. melitensis* infection in sheep. It should be given to lambs and kids aged between 3 and 5 months as a single subcutaneous or conjunctival inoculation. No matter the inoculation route, the standard dose must be between 0.5×10^9 and 2.0×10^9 viable organisms. The subcutaneous vaccination induces long lasting serological responses, causing

strong interferences in serological tests and should not be recommended for use in combined eradication programmes. However, when this vaccine is administered conjunctivally at the standard dose, it produces a similar protection without inducing a persistent antibody response, thus facilitating the application of eradication programmes combined with vaccination. Care must be taken when using *B. melitensis* Rev.1 vaccine to avoid the risk of contaminating the environment or causing human infection.

Vaccination in pigs: Attempts have been made to develop a suitable vaccine to immunize pigs against *B. suis*, but none has been found fully effective. Only *Brucella suis* strain 2 (S2), has been reported effective after extensive field use in China (People's Rep. of) (in pigs and other species), but efficacy data against *B. suis* infection under strictly controlled conditions are not available. Oral or intramuscular immunization with killed *B. suis*, RB51, or purified O-polysaccharide was reported to be efficacious in protecting swine exposed to infected boars. However, other studies have shown very little protection by strain RB51 in immunized swine against wild type challenge.

Subunit Vaccine

Subunit vaccines which are derived from virulent organism like recombinant proteins, are promising vaccine candidates because they are well defined, less biohazardous, avirulent, noninfectious, and nonviable.

Recombinant Vaccine

For development of effective recombinant vaccine selection of optimal antigen is most crucial and immune response mainly depends on T & B cell epitope presents in the antigen. The protection against the organism depends on type of desired immune response required against a particular pathogen. Several *Brucella* proteins have been used as immunogens for experimental subunit vaccine formulations, including outer membrane proteins, namely Omp16, Omp19, Omp31, Omp28, and Omp25, ribosomal protein L7/L12 Cu-Zn superoxide dismutase, a cytoplasmic protein p39, lumazine synthase BLS, among others. But most of these vaccines are still in experimental stage.

DNA Vaccines

A DNA vaccine is a type of vaccine that transfects a specific antigen-coding DNA sequence into the cells of an organism and elicit an immune response. In DNA vaccines plasmid containing sequence of target antigen against which an immune response is sought is injected into the body so the cells directly produce the antigen, thus causing a protective immunological response. Unlike live attenuated vaccines DNA vaccines are safe and they have ability to induce both humoral and cell mediated immune responses. DNA vaccine targeting Omp31, L7/L12 and P39 genes, BSCP31 (31 kDa protein), Cu/Zn SOD genes individually or in combination have been tried successfully in mice model. One of the advantages of DNA vaccines is that multiple antigens can be expressed using same vector. The coadministration of multiple plasmids expressing BSCP31 (31 kDa protein), Cu/Zn SOD, or L7/L12 have been found to have enhanced the protection against *B. abortus*. The coadministration of antigen along with some cytokine as adjuvants has also been found to have better immune response. When genes encoding IL-2 or IL-18 were fused to SOD and expressed in a single DNA vaccine, improved protection was observed compared to a SOD DNA vaccine

alone.

Vectored Vaccines

A vectored vaccine is a vaccine that uses a viral/bacterial vector to deliver genetic material coding for a desired antigen into the recipient's host cells. Vector vaccines enable antigen expression within cells and induce a robust cytotoxic T cell response, unlike subunit vaccines which only confer humoral immunity. Antigen delivery systems become necessary when antigens are not efficiently transported to the appropriate sites or presented to the immune system. Recently, a vectored vaccine targeting several genes L7/L12 (ribosomal protein) Cu-Zn SOD BP26 or Omp16 and Omp31 as well as vectors like *E. coli* (K12), *Lactococcus lactis* Semliki Forest Virus (SFV) have been attempted with varying degree of success. *E. coli* expressing *B. melitensis* BP26 induced lymphocyte proliferation, IFN- γ production, and protection in mice. *Lactococcus lactis* expressing Cu-Zn SOD has also been used as a delivery system in mouse model and induced protection against a *B. abortus* challenge. Semliki Forest Virus (SFV) was packed with RNA encoding the *B. abortus* Cu-Zn SOD and was able to induce protection in mice against *B. abortus*.

DIVA Vaccine

DIVA (Differentiating Infected from vaccinated animals) vaccines are originally deletion mutants of wild microorganism strains. Diagnostic tests should be used with these vaccines to identify antibodies against the epitopes. DIVA vaccines are generally based upon the lack of minimal one immunogenic protein in the vaccine strain. In the DIVA strategy, after vaccination with the DIVA vaccines, diagnostic tests are used to determine antibodies against antigens that are not in the vaccine strain. This system makes it possible to mass vaccinate as well as to allow serological follow-up of a sensitive animal population for effective disease control.

Synthetic peptide vaccines

The highly selective epitope of antigens capable of activating the immune system can be selected as vaccine candidates. The formulation of these vaccines is synthetic peptide. Complete Freund's adjuvant (CFA) or incomplete Freund's adjuvant (IFA) is used in vaccines. It was reported that synthetic peptide (GGAPGEKDKGKIVPAG) of *B. abortus* Cu-Zn SOD possessed protective biological activity, which was able to modulate both splenomegaly and the extent of *Brucella* infection in mouse spleen. However, in general, this class of vaccine displays relatively low protection. This drawback eventually prompted the interruption of development of the synthetic peptide vaccine.

Conclusion

Vaccination is a determinant strategy for brucellosis control and eradication programs therefore it has been the target of innumerable studies over decades. Nowadays, some effective vaccines are available to control the disease in cattle. S19 and RB51 are the officially approved *B. abortus* vaccine strains more widely and successfully used to prevent bovine brucellosis worldwide. However, there are ongoing, intensive efforts focused on the development of new and better vaccinations due to various side effects revealed by these

present vaccines, as well as the advancements in recombinant DNA technology and the lack of a vaccine for humans.

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